

European Union green deal in action: Harnessing consumer preferences to drive pesticide reduction in winegrowing

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ABSTRACT

This study determines consumers' willingness to pay (WTP) for wines with reduced pesticide use in the EU Mediterranean region in the context of the European Commission's Green Deal objective to halve pesticide use by 2030, a goal that has faced significant political and practical challenges. A dynamic reference-dependent discrete choice experiment (DCE) involving over 4000 wine consumers from France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain was conducted. This innovative pivot design incorporates consumer-specific reference points based on previous purchases into a two-stage choice framework, enabling a more realistic estimation of willingness to pay in a market characterized by diverse wine attributes and price ranges. The study tests eight hypotheses related to WTP for pesticide reduction, certification type, and personal factors influencing consumer decisions. The results show that conventional winegrowers who reduce pesticide use by up to 40 % could command price premiums of approximately 26 % in France, 29 % in Greece, 30 % in Italy and Portugal, and 28 % in Spain compared with standard conventional practices. Certification by EU-approved third-party entities consistently generated the highest consumer trust and WTP. Furthermore, sociodemographics, subjective knowledge, environmental attitudes, economic capacity, consumer involvement, and exploratory behavior significantly influence consumers' WTP. The findings reveal a market opportunity for pesticide-reduced conventional wines and demonstrate that consumer preferences could serve as a viable incentive for the voluntary adoption of sustainable practices in viticulture. While generalizability may be influenced by sampling, as well as cultural and institutional differences, the results provide practical insights into untapped market-based incentives that could be leveraged to drive pesticide reduction in the absence of binding EU regulations.

1. Introduction

Plant protection products, commonly known as pesticides, play pivotal roles in modern agriculture, mitigating crop diseases and significantly protecting yields (Schneider et al., 2023; Tudi et al., 2021). Without pesticides, global production is estimated to decline by 78 % for fruits, 54 % for vegetables, and 35 % for cereals (Tudi et al., 2021). In the European Union (EU), research shows that reducing pesticide use could lower food production between 3 % and 30 %, depending on the crop, with tree crops such as olives, grapes, and apples being the most affected (Bremmer et al., 2021; Schneider et al., 2023). However, these benefits come with significant environmental and societal costs.

Pesticide use has been linked to environmental pollution, biodiversity loss, and adverse public health outcomes (Finger and Möhring, 2024; Tang et al., 2021), raising concerns about its long-term sustainability. The EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy aimed to address these issues by originally proposing a 50 % reduction in pesticide use and associated risks by 2030 (Wesseler, 2022). However, the recent withdrawal of supporting legislation, the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Regulation (SUR), has left the reduction targets largely dependent on the voluntary action of farmers.

The viticulture sector, which is among the most intensive users of pesticides, exemplifies the complexities of balancing agricultural productivity with sustainability (Fouillet et al., 2022; Urruty et al., 2016).

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Research has identified pesticide use in vineyard operations as a major environmental hotspot that contributes to soil biodiversity loss (Cerdà et al., 2021), water pollution (Bony, 2008), and risks to plant and human health (Petit et al., 2008; Raheison et al., 2019). While regulatory measures such as the now suspended SUR are important, achieving meaningful pesticide reduction may also require the active involvement of other stakeholders, particularly consumers. Consumer choices directly influence demand for sustainably produced food, as evidenced by the growing market for organic and locally sourced products (Frehner et al., 2022; Vittersø and Tangeland, 2015). However, little is known about consumers' willingness to support pesticide reduction efforts in conventional agriculture, especially in the wine sector, which holds significant cultural and economic value in the EU Mediterranean region.

A growing body of literature has examined consumer preferences for sustainable wines, particularly organic, biodynamic, and natural wines. These preferences are largely driven by perceived health and environmental benefits, often outweighing sensory considerations such as taste (Scozzafava et al., 2021). Organic certification, in particular, has emerged as the most influential environmental claim in shaping wine choices (Tait et al., 2019), with associated premiums typically ranging from approximately 9%–36% (Vecchio et al., 2023; Fanasch and Frick, 2020). Biodynamic wines tend to attract more modest premiums (4–13%) and are perceived as more niche. Some studies also report premiums of up to 19% for wines labeled more broadly as “sustainable,” especially when backed by credible certification schemes (Delmas and Grant, 2014; Valenzuela et al., 2022). Across these segments, key determinants of willingness to pay (WTP¹) include health consciousness, environmental concern, certification trust, and sociodemographic factors such as age, gender, and wine involvement (Modica et al., 2025; Gow et al., 2022; Moscovici et al., 2022).

Despite the growing interest in certified sustainable wines, little attention has been given to consumer preferences for conventional wines produced with reduced pesticide use, a practice with strong environmental implications but often lacking formal sustainable certification. Existing studies typically treat sustainability as a bundled attribute, focusing on labels such as “organic” or “biodynamic,” which combine multiple environmental and processing requirements, including reduced input use, biodiversity protection, fermentation methods, and soil management. This bundling makes it difficult to isolate how consumers value specific sustainable practices. Moreover, only a few studies (Borrello et al., 2024) have examined consumer WTP for products from technologies that encourage incremental sustainability, such as precision spraying, disease-resistant grape varieties, or robotic weed control, which can substantially reduce pesticide use in conventional systems without requiring a full transition to organic farming (Casanova-Gascón et al., 2019; Paleari et al., 2024; Salas et al., 2024). These technologies offer promising pathways for more environmentally friendly production among conventional farmers, who may face financial or regulatory barriers to full organic transition.

This study investigates consumer preferences and WTP for wines with reduced pesticide use, independent of sustainable certification. Focusing on five Mediterranean EU countries—France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain, where wine production is both culturally and economically embedded, this study also examines how consumer trust in certification bodies affects purchasing behavior. In addition, it explores the socioeconomic and attitudinal factors shaping WTP for pesticide-reduced wines. Specifically, the study addresses the following questions: What is the WTP among EU consumers for conventional wines produced with reduced pesticide use? How do consumers value different certifying entities, such as EU third-party bodies versus private or

producer-led schemes? Which personal and behavioral characteristics influence these preferences? How do they vary across countries with different wine cultures and consumption patterns?

To address these questions, we employ a dynamic reference-dependent discrete choice experiment, where each respondent's most recent wine purchase anchors a personalized set of choice scenarios. This approach enhances external validity by simulating realistic decision-making contexts, which is particularly important in a product category that is heterogeneous and experience-based, such as wine. The study offers four key contributions to the literature. First, it isolates consumer valuation of pesticide reduction from broader, often bundled, sustainability claims, offering a clearer view of how specific practices are perceived. Second, it evaluates the signaling strength of different certification schemes, shedding light on their relative credibility and effectiveness. Third, it explores cross-country variation in WTP across five Mediterranean EU countries with long-standing wine traditions, providing valuable comparative insights. Finally, anchoring the choice experiment on each respondent's most recent wine purchase introduces realistic market conditions, ensuring that attribute levels reflect familiar price and quality ranges.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the hypotheses derived from different consumer preference theories and the literature. Section 3 outlines the materials and methods used to address the research objectives. Section 4 presents the results, followed by Section 5, which discusses the findings, including practical and policy implications and limitations. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Literature review and hypotheses

The wine sector offers a compelling context for analyzing sustainability and consumer WTP, given its cultural, economic, and environmental significance. Economically, wine production constitutes a major segment of the global agri-food industry, with growing demand in both traditional and emerging markets (Correia et al., 2019). Culturally, wine holds symbolic and ritual value in many societies, especially in Mediterranean Europe, where it reflects a blend of heritage and innovation (Alessandri et al., 2024; Charters et al., 2022). Concurrently, the wine industry has evolved from a producer-driven model to one increasingly shaped by consumer expectations and sustainability imperatives (Dressler and Paunovic, 2021). As a result, wine occupies a unique position in academic sustainability debates, where it is examined not only for its environmental footprint but also for its role in signaling responsible production and consumption.

Although sustainability is defined in various ways, the most widely accepted framework encompasses three interrelated dimensions: environmental soundness, economic feasibility, and social equity (Purvis et al., 2019). The International Organization of Vine and Wine (OIV, 2016) also recognizes cultural factors within the sustainability agenda, although these factors are typically embedded within the broader social dimension (Flores, 2018). From a viticultural perspective, sustainability entails reducing chemical inputs, preserving biodiversity, maintaining economic viability, and supporting rural livelihoods (Baiano, 2021). Sustainable winegrowing thus involves a holistic approach that seeks to enhance ecosystem services and minimize environmental impact while simultaneously delivering socioeconomic benefits (Borrello et al., 2024). This integration of environmental, economic, and social goals positions sustainable wine as a premium product (Wei et al., 2023), contributing to cost efficiency, competitiveness, and consumer satisfaction (Santini et al., 2013).

Given the increasing importance of food consumers in shaping market demand, a growing body of literature has examined consumer preferences for sustainable wines, particularly those labeled as organic, biodynamic, or natural. These labels often command price premiums because of consumer perceptions of health benefits, environmental protection, and ethical production methods (Vecchio et al., 2023; Valenzuela et al., 2022). Studies report WTP premiums ranging from 8

¹ Willingness to pay (WTP) refers to the maximum amount that a consumer is prepared to spend on a novel or non-market product as a result of the additional utility derived (Lusk and Hudson, 2004). Hereafter, the acronym WTP is used throughout the study.

% to over 36 % for organic wines, with certification trust and sustainability awareness among the key determinants of higher WTP (Mauracher et al., 2019; Sogari et al., 2016). However, such labels typically bundle multiple sustainability practices, making it difficult to isolate consumer valuations of specific practices, especially those at the grape cultivation stage, such as pesticide reduction, which is central to EU sustainability targets.

Moreover, wine is a highly complex product with purchasing decisions shaped by a variety of overlapping attributes beyond sustainability. These include brand reputation, price, region of origin (PDO/PGI), grape variety, alcohol content, vintage, sensory attributes, and even consumption occasion (Robertson et al., 2018; Capitello et al., 2016; Palma et al., 2013). For example, Boncinelli et al. (2019) reported that Italian consumers prioritize value and origin when purchasing for personal use but place more weight on organic status and brand when buying wine as a gift. Designation of origin strongly influences perceptions of quality and authenticity, yet preferences often vary across regions, even within the same PDO or PGI category (Hertzberg and Malorgio, 2008; Capitello et al., 2016). Furthermore, prices play several roles in wine choices, e.g., segmenting consumers (Costanigro et al., 2007; Zanchini et al., 2024) or as a signal of quality (Palma et al., 2013). Additionally, interactions among attributes (e.g., high price and PDO) reinforce quality expectations within certain consumer segments, particularly among experienced buyers (Perrouy et al., 2006; McCutcheon et al., 2009). These overlapping factors and interactions highlight the complexity of the wine market and the multifaceted nature of consumer preferences.

Consequently, isolating consumers' willingness to pay for specific sustainability attributes, such as pesticide reduction, requires an innovative, context-sensitive approach that accounts for broader consumer preferences. This is particularly important given evidence that consumers often interpret new quality cues or certifications in relation to existing labels, as demonstrated in studies on geographical indications of wines (Costanigro et al., 2019). To address the challenge of estimating WTP for pesticide reduction amid consumer heterogeneity and market complexity, our choice design is anchored in consumers' most recent wine purchases rather than being presented in isolation. We employ a dynamic reference-dependent discrete choice experiment, using each respondent's last purchase as a personalized reference point. This two-stage design enables more realistic WTP estimates by grounding choices in actual behavior and accounting for heterogeneity in preferences, price sensitivity, and product familiarity while also capturing individual variation in the consumption context.

Against this backdrop, we formulate a set of hypotheses grounded in established consumer behavior theory and prior empirical research. These hypotheses examine willingness to pay for pesticide reduction in conventional wines, differences across certification types, and the influence of six key factors: sociodemographics, subjective knowledge, environmental attitudes, economic capacity, consumer involvement, and exploratory behavior.

2.1. Pesticide reduction and consumer WTP

Many studies have assessed consumer preferences and WTP a premium for wines with sustainable attributes (Forbes et al., 2009; Pomarici and Vecchio, 2014; Schäufele and Hamm, 2017). However, most works on consumer behavior toward sustainable environmental attributes in wine production have focused on organic, biodynamic, and natural practices (Maesano et al., 2021; Schäufele and Hamm, 2017; Vecchio et al., 2023). Studies that go beyond organic practices often use the term "sustainable wines" without clarifying which particular sustainable attributes they consider (Sgroi et al., 2023). This emphasis on organic and similar related practices tends to overlook other environmental approaches lacking approved sustainable certification. While organic practices are widely regarded as benchmarks for sustainability in viticulture, other methods, such as integrated pest management,

precision agriculture, and agroecological practices, also contribute significantly to sustainable environmental production. These approaches can help reduce chemical pesticide use, conserve water, and lower production costs (Gil et al., 2023; H. Nguyen, 2018; Romero et al., 2022; Wezel et al., 2020).

Despite these benefits, the impact of pesticide reduction alone, independent of full sustainable certification, has received little attention in consumer WTP research. This creates fragmented insights into how consumers value pesticide reduction as a sustainable winegrowing practice. Existing studies suggest that consumers are willing to pay a premium for organic wines with zero pesticide use compared to conventional wines (Scozzafava et al., 2021; Vecchio et al., 2023). This suggests that consumers may value wines with reduced pesticide use more highly than standard conventional options.

Furthermore, drawing on the value-belief-norm (VBN) theory, which links pro-environmental values to purchasing behaviors (Hiratsuka et al., 2018), it is plausible that consumers with strong environmental values would support pesticide reduction as an essential sustainable practice. Additionally, many wine consumers are in a transitional phase moving toward adopting sustainable wine behaviors (Pickering, 2023). Therefore, wine consumers may be open to supporting sustainable practices such as pesticide reduction, leading to the following hypothesis:

H1. Wine consumers are willing to pay a significant premium for conventional wines with reduced pesticide use, recognizing it as a key sustainable environmental attribute.

2.2. Certification and WTP for pesticide reduction

The mechanisms for communicating and achieving a price premium for adopting sustainable practices have been widely discussed. However, it remains uncertain whether certifications consistently hold clear value for consumers (Delmas and Gergaud, 2021; van 't Veld, 2020). Certifications serve to verify that management practices meet established minimum standards (Delmas and Grant, 2014). This process typically involves a recognized entity affirming that a product or organization complies with specific criteria, often signified by the issuance of labels (Delmas and Gergaud, 2021).

While some studies indicate that winegrowers can secure higher prices by self-declaring sustainable practices (Fanasch and Frick, 2020), certifications are often deemed essential for establishing the credibility of such claims. They differentiate products by emphasizing sustainable attributes, enhancing the perceived reliability of quality claims, and supporting higher price premiums (Fanasch and Frick, 2020; Yang et al., 2020). In the context of sustainable winegrowing, certifications assure buyers that the winemaking process adheres to specific guidelines that are distinct from those of conventional methods (Parga Dans et al., 2019; Sogari et al., 2015). Understanding consumers' WTP for wines produced with reduced pesticide use, therefore, requires insights into the channel through which sustainable attributes are communicated and perceived.

The wine industry offers a wide array of certifications and eco-labels to verify sustainability attributes. However, the abundance of logos can make it challenging for consumers to discern credible certifications (Baldoni, 2020; Delmas and Gergaud, 2021; Parga Dans et al., 2019). Since the effectiveness of sustainable certifications depends heavily on consumer trust, credibility is a critical factor (Sogari et al., 2015). The signaling, consumer trust, and credence attribute theories provide a useful framework for analyzing these dynamics. Pesticide use, as a credence attribute, cannot be directly observed or verified by consumers, unlike search or experience attributes (Baron, 2011). Consequently, consumer acceptance of such attributes depends on trust, as explained by consumer trust theories (Bozic, 2017). Signaling theory emphasizes the importance of credible entities or mechanisms to bridge the information gap between producers and buyers, thus reducing information asymmetry (Osburg et al., 2022).

In the EU wine industry, various eco-labels have emerged from different certifying agencies (Delmas and Gergaud, 2021; Delmas and Grant, 2014; Delmas and Lessem, 2017). These certifications include those issued by third-party organizations endorsed by public authorities, as well as private initiatives or farmer-led efforts without formal endorsement (Cuéllar-Padilla and Ganuza-Fernandez, 2018; Lemeilleur and Allaire, 2016). Third-party certifications, which rely on independent audits, are widely regarded as more credible because impartial oversight minimizes conflicts of interest (Bass et al., 2001; Castka and Corbett, 2016; Delmas and Gergaud, 2021). In the EU, third-party certifiers may include government or EU-approved entities or authorized private organizations tasked with ensuring compliance (Cuéllar-Padilla and Ganuza-Fernandez, 2018).

Beyond third-party certifications, first- or second-party certifications, such as participatory guarantee systems (PGSs), are gaining traction in the food sector (Wilier and Lernoud, 2015). The International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements defines PGS as “locally focused quality assurance systems that certify producers based on the active participation of stakeholders and are built on a foundation of trust, social networks, and knowledge exchange” (Kaufmann and Vogl, 2018).

As the credibility of certifications often hinges on the entity behind them, it is vital to determine which certifying bodies wine consumers perceive as most trustworthy for conveying information about sustainable practices, such as pesticide reduction. Given the EU’s leadership in promoting pesticide reduction, it is reasonable to expect that certifications backed by EU-approved entities are perceived as more credible than claims made by other entities. Thus, following the credence-signaling-trust framework, it is plausible that consumers would place a higher premium on certifications by EU-approved entities regarding pesticide reduction. Accordingly, we propose the following:

H2. Compared with certifications from other entities, EU-approved certifications result in greater consumer WTP for wines with reduced pesticide use because of greater perceived credibility and trust.

2.3. Determinants of consumer WTP for wine with reduced pesticides

2.3.1. Demographic characteristics

The link between consumers’ WTP for sustainable food products and their sociodemographic characteristics has been explored in several studies, revealing consistent trends in consumer behavior. While not all studies agree on the strength or nature of these relationships, socio-demographic factors such as age, gender,² education, and income have frequently been shown to influence WTP for sustainable products (Schäufele and Hamm, 2017; Sogari et al., 2016). For example, Singh and Verma (2017) reported that age, education, and income significantly affect the decision to purchase sustainable products, such as organic foods. Similarly, Muresan et al. (2021) highlighted that age and education were key factors shaping consumer attitudes toward sustainable food choices. A comprehensive review of analyses of consumer WTP for organic foods between 1999 and 2019 revealed that nearly half identified age, gender, and education as significant predictors of WTP (Katt and Meixner, 2020).

Although a range of sociodemographic characteristics have been studied in relation to WTP for sustainable products, research consistently suggests that younger consumers, females, those with higher levels of education, and incomes are more likely to engage in sustainable consumption behaviors (Gilg et al., 2005; Gomes et al., 2023; Uliano et al., 2024). These groups are often more health-conscious and tend to prioritize sustainability, influencing their attitudes toward premium products (Diamantopoulos et al., 2003; Zelezny et al., 2000). In line with

existing findings on the role of these demographics in shaping consumer preferences for sustainable products, the following hypotheses have been formulated:

H3a. Younger consumers are more likely to exhibit higher WTP for wines with reduced pesticide use than older consumers are, driven by greater environmental awareness and sustainability concerns.

H3b. Female consumers are more willing to pay a premium for wines with reduced pesticide use than male consumers are due to stronger health-conscious and pro-environmental attitudes.

H3c. Consumers with higher levels of education demonstrate greater WTP for wines with reduced pesticide use, reflecting an increased awareness of sustainability and environmental impacts.

2.3.2. Environmental knowledge

Researchers have identified environmental knowledge, which is often posited as a key driver of green consumption, as a crucial factor in shaping green attitudes and behaviors (Barber et al., 2009; Johnstone and Tan, 2015). This assumption is based on a linear progression model that suggests that increased knowledge leads to greater environmental awareness and concern, resulting in the promotion of pro-environmental behavior (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002). Indeed, studies have shown that information, awareness, and sustainability-related knowledge significantly influence consumer behavior and sustainable purchasing decisions (O’Rourke and Ringer, 2016; Okur and Saricam, 2019; Onel and Mukherjee, 2016). Studies that attempt to address the attitude-behavior gap in sustainable consumption suggest that enhancing information and awareness can bridge the gap between consumers’ intentions and actions (Ran et al., 2022).

Further evidence suggests that knowledge about environmental impacts positively affects consumer choices toward sustainable products. For instance, Taufique et al. (2016) reported that both general environmental knowledge and eco-label knowledge positively influence consumer attitudes, fostering ecologically conscious behavior. Similarly, Khaleeli and Jawabri (2021) and Maniatis (2016) reported positive relationships between environmental awareness and purchase intentions for eco-friendly products. Furthermore, Sellers-Rubio and Nicolau-Gonzalbez (2016) suggested that increased environmental knowledge is correlated with greater WTP premiums for sustainable products.

Some authors have highlighted the difficulty in proving the relationship between environmental knowledge and sustainable purchases, particularly with respect to whether it is subjective or objective knowledge that influences green behavior (Barber et al., 2009). However, Amyx et al. (1994) reported that subjective knowledge, consumers’ perception of their knowledge, better predicts ecological purchasing intentions than does the objective type. This suggests that consumers who perceive themselves as environmentally knowledgeable are more likely to make sustainable purchases than those with factual knowledge but have lower confidence in their understanding.

In this study, we examine the impact of consumers’ subjective knowledge of pesticide use on their preferences for wines produced with reduced pesticide use. Additionally, we investigate whether providing information about specific innovations in pesticide reduction further enhances subjective knowledge and influences WTP, based on the following hypotheses:

H4a. Consumers’ subjective knowledge about pesticide use in vineyards positively influences their WTP for wines with reduced pesticide use.

H4b. Exposure to information about innovations used to reduce pesticide use in vineyards increases consumers’ subjective knowledge, which in turn increases their WTP for sustainable wines.

² In this study, we use the term “gender” in reference to participants who identified themselves as males or females, as reported in the survey data.

2.3.3. Environmental attitude

In multiattribute models such as the theory of reasoned action (TRA) (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1977) and the theory of planned behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), attitudes are understood to shape behavioral intentions, which in turn influence actual behavior. Thus, attitudes are widely recognized as primary drivers of human behavior (Bredahl, 2001). For example, research shows that consumers with strong pro-environmental attitudes often prefer sustainable products and spend more on organic wines (Schäufele and Hamm, 2018). Similarly, studies by Joshi and Rahman (2017) and Nandi et al. (2017) demonstrate that environmental concerns significantly affect green purchasing behavior and WTP for eco-friendly products.

In the wine sector, evidence indicates a strong positive relationship between environmental attitudes and the willingness to purchase sustainable wines; consumers with positive environmental attitudes are more likely to consider purchasing eco-labeled wines (Barber et al., 2009). Sogari et al. (2016) reported that consumers with strong pro-environmental attitudes were willing to pay a higher premium for sustainably labeled wine. Although there is no universally accepted definition of environmental attitudes, Gifford and Sussman (2012) define them as “concern for the environment or caring about environmental issues.” Moreover, research shows that consumers’ environmental concerns significantly affect their attitudes toward sustainable foods (Hu et al., 2024). Consequently, we consider that consumers with greater environmental concerns hold positive attitudes toward sustainable products and posit the following:

H5. Consumers with greater concerns about the environmental impact of pesticides in vineyards are willing to pay more for wines with reduced pesticide use.

2.3.4. Economic situation

Situational factors, such as economic constraints, can impact green consumption behavior, particularly in sectors such as wine (Johnstone and Tan, 2015). Studies on economic factors, including product price, income levels, and employment status, consistently show that they influence purchasing decisions (Janssen, 2018; Singh and Verma, 2017). For example, general wine consumption per capita has been linked to broader economic conditions, indicating that during economic downturns, consumers may favor more affordable options, potentially reducing their preference for sustainable wines, which are often priced higher than conventional alternatives (Schaefer et al., 2018).

Research highlights wine price and consumer income as key determinants of wine choice and consumption (Camillo, 2012; Stanciu and Neagu, 2014). Higher-income consumers are reported to have stronger intentions toward sustainability attributes (Schäufele and Hamm, 2017; Sellers, 2016; Uliano et al., 2024). Pomarici et al. (2016) also reported that higher spenders are more oriented toward sustainability.

Furthermore, research indicates that there is a relationship between higher previous prices and a greater WTP for sustainable products, as explained by reference price theory (Anton et al., 2023; Weaver and Frederick, 2012). Consumers who regularly pay higher prices for a product are more likely to perceive premium prices as acceptable, which positively influences their WTP for additional attributes, such as sustainability. On these bases, the following hypotheses are proposed, considering consumers’ income levels and their prior price experiences with wine:

H6a. Consumers with higher incomes exhibit a greater WTP for wines with reduced pesticide use because of their increased financial ability and potential prioritization of sustainability.

H6b. Consumers who have previously purchased higher-priced wines are more willing to pay more for wines with reduced pesticide use, reflecting their familiarity with higher pricing.

2.3.5. Consumer involvement

The concept of consumer involvement has been classified into several streams on the basis of different psychological analyses. The streams most commonly used in consumer studies are enduring and situational involvements, which refer to long-term interest and temporary engagement, respectively (Barber et al., 2009). While enduring involvement reflects a consistent, general interest in a product, the situational type is driven by specific contexts or conditions.

Previous research conceptualizes enduring involvement as the extent to which a consumer views purchasing or consuming wine as meaningful, central, or engaging (Charters and Pettigrew, 2007). Wine consumers’ level of involvement was found to influence both purchase intentions and WTP (Corsi et al., 2022; Hollebeek et al., 2007). The reason is that high involvement in wine is correlated with greater knowledge and experience, which often leads consumers to engage in more extensive information seeking during purchase decisions (Bonn et al., 2016). For example, highly involved consumers tend to emphasize the cognitive attributes of wine, such as complexity, whereas less involved consumers prioritize sensory attributes, such as taste or smoothness (Charters and Pettigrew, 2007).

In the literature, involvement has been further divided into product involvement, which reflects consumers’ personal perceptions of wine importance, and purchase involvement, which focuses on the relevance of wine purchase activities (Bonn et al., 2016; Drichoutis et al., 2007; Karaatli, 2015). We test these two dimensions of involvement by hypothesizing the following:

H7a. Consumers with high wine involvement, characterized by greater knowledge and personal interest in wine, exhibit greater WTP for wines with reduced pesticide use.

H7b. Consumers with a higher purchase frequency, reflecting habitual engagement with wine purchasing, are willing to pay more for wines with reduced pesticide use.

2.3.6. Exploratory behavior

Consumer exploratory behavior refers to the inclination to try novel, innovative products and the tendency to switch among familiar options (Muñoz et al., 2019; Schaefer et al., 2018). This concept is rooted in the theory of optimum stimulation level (OSL), which suggests that consumers seek a balanced level of stimulation, enough to avoid boredom but not so intense as to be overwhelming (Orth and Bourrain, 2005). Consumers with a high level of exploratory behavior are attracted to novelty and like to experience unfamiliar products, often valuing creativity, excitement, and the thrill of risk-taking over adherence to convention (Schaefer et al., 2018).

In general, only consumers who are more exploratory and risk-tolerant are inclined to embrace new or unconventional products because of the perceived risks associated with them (Orth and Bourrain, 2005). Some studies have explored a related concept, wine neophobia (i. e., consumers’ willingness or reluctance to try new wines), which parallels the concept of food neophobia developed by Pliner and Hobden (Pickering et al., 2021; Pliner and Hobden, 1992; Rabadán, 2021a). This parallel may be somewhat strong in regard to consumers’ preference for wine produced with reduced pesticide use. However, OSL theory, which posits that exploratory consumers are more receptive to novel experiences, presupposes that consumers with greater exploratory tendencies may be more open to wines with limited pesticides, seeing them as both innovative and in line with their interest in new experiences. This leads to our hypothesis:

H8. Consumers with high exploratory behavior, characterized by openness to novel and innovative products, exhibit greater WTP for wines produced with reduced pesticide use.

3. Methods

3.1. Study area data collection

The data were collected from France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain, five of the leading wine-producing nations in the EU. Together, France, Italy, and Spain account for nearly three-quarters (74.9 %) of all EU vineyards (EUROSTAT, 2017). These countries are also among the top wine consumers in Europe, with annual per capita consumption rates of 45.8 L in France, 15.9 L in Greece, 42.1 L in Italy, 61.7 L in Portugal, and 24.0 L in Spain (OIV, 2024).

However, a critical issue in these winegrowing regions is the extensive use of pesticides, driven by the susceptibility of grapes to pests and diseases. The average current pesticide use per hectare of cropland is 3.6 kg in France and Spain, 6.1 kg in Italy, 5.5 kg in Portugal, and 2.9 kg in Greece (FAOSTAT, 2024). The rates of pesticide use in vineyards are significantly higher due to their specialized agricultural requirements, which can occasionally lead to trace residues being detected in wines (Martín-García et al., 2024).

As part of the original EU's Green Deal target to halve pesticide use and the associated risks by 2030, the viticulture sector continues to explore innovative solutions to promote sustainable winegrowing. One such initiative is the EU Horizon project, NOVATERRA, under which alternative pesticide-reducing technologies have been developed for vineyards. For example, a smart real-time canopy characterization innovation has been designed to optimize pesticide application, reducing usage by up to 40 % without compromising pest control effectiveness (Gil et al., 2023). Currently being implemented across the five countries, the technology requires an initial investment and annual maintenance by winegrowers. These extra production costs could eventually be passed to consumers within the wine value chain if they are not absorbed in the form of subsidies.

This study gathered data from nationally representative wine consumers in the five countries covered by the NOVATERRA project to assess their readiness to support conventional winegrowers' efforts to adopt such pesticide-reducing innovations through their purchase decisions. Data collection was conducted via the Qualtrics® consumer panel platform, which targeted consumers who had purchased conventional wines for regular home consumption within the three months preceding the survey, which took place between January and March 2024.

A total of 4083 randomly selected wine consumers from the consumer panel database of Qualtrics® in the five member states consented to participate in the survey. Participation was restricted to wine consumers aged 18 or older who were mainly responsible for purchasing wines. Furthermore, the quota sampling technique was used to ensure equal representation of countries, genders and age groups.

Data collection adhered to ethical research standards based on the Helsinki and Belmont declarations, with strict attention to safeguarding anonymity, confidentiality, and privacy in accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The study also received ethical approval (2–2024) from the ethical committee of the Research Center for Agrofood Economics and Development (CREDA). All the respondents provided informed consent after receiving a comprehensive overview of the study.

3.2. Survey implementation

The survey was conducted using a structured questionnaire divided into three main parts. The first part included questions on wine-purchasing habits, such as purchase frequency, level of involvement in purchase decisions, and wine consumption patterns. It also covered key factors considered in the respondents' most recent conventional wine purchases, including the brand/label, vintage, alcohol content, country of origin, and price. This part served as a filter to identify regular wine consumers who were primarily responsible for purchase decisions and

had bought conventional red wine within the three months prior to the survey.

Based on the responses to the filter questions, such as “Are you responsible for buying wine for your household?” and “Have you purchased conventional red wine in the last three months?”, respondents were either granted or restricted from access to the second and third parts of the survey questionnaire.

In the second part, information about respondents' most recent purchases was used as a reference for a dynamic reference price-dependent discrete choice experiment (DCE). The details of the DCE method are presented in Section 3.3.

The third part collected additional sociodemographic information, beyond age and gender (with the latter two used as quota variables to ensure diverse consumer representations in the survey). It also included questions about respondents' environmental attitudes, perceptions, wine involvement, and exploratory scales, allowing us to test all the hypotheses in the study.

The questionnaire was originally designed in English and later translated into the respective languages of the five countries (i.e., French, Greek, Italian, Portuguese, and Spanish) with the assistance of language and wine experts. Emphasis was placed on accurately translating key terms, such as “pesticide reduction,” “certifications,” and “conventional wine,” to ensure consistent contextual meaning across all the languages. A total of 50 pre-survey tests were conducted in each of the five countries to validate the design. Feedback was used to refine the final questions for the survey.

3.3. Dynamic reference price-dependent discrete choice experiment

The discrete choice experiment method is widely used to elicit consumer and producer preferences by simulating purchase decisions in hypothetical market scenarios (Lizin et al., 2022). In a DCE, respondents are presented with a series of product alternatives that vary in attributes and price, allowing estimation of trade-offs and WTP (Contini et al., 2019). Despite their advantages, DCEs often face design challenges related to price vectors, attribute selection, and hypothetical bias (Bosworth and Taylor, 2012; Hanley et al., 2005; Jacquemet et al., 2013). To mitigate some of these concerns, we employed a dynamic reference-dependent DCE supplemented by “cheap talk” and “solemn oath” scripts to reduce hypothetical bias.

Given that consumers often draw on past experiences to evaluate new choices (Kim et al., 2020), our DCE was pivoted on each respondent's most recent conventional wine purchase, defined as the “reference wine” (Larvoe and Kallas, 2025). This approach builds on behavioral economics research showing that consumers assess value through comparisons, evaluating gains and losses relative to a known reference (Hess and Rose, 2009). By anchoring choices to a personally relevant reference point, the design enhances realism and accurate WTP estimation, particularly for wines, where preferences are highly heterogeneous and context sensitive.

The reference wine framework also serves a second purpose: it allows important product characteristics such as alcohol content, brand, origin (e.g., PDO/PGI), taste, packaging, and price to be indirectly accounted for in the choice tasks, even though they are not explicitly included. This strategy reduces the cognitive burden while preserving the decision-making context, enabling respondents to focus on the attributes of interest.

The link between the consumers' reference wine and the choice alternatives was achieved through a dynamic survey framework in Qualtrics® (Weber, 2021), where information from each respondent's most recent purchase was incorporated into the DCE.

In summary, the dynamic reference-dependent DCE enabled us to estimate consumer WTP for pesticide reduction and certification while implicitly controlling for other influential wine attributes. Although this approach does not eliminate the limitations associated with narrow attribute sets, it helps balance design simplicity with contextual

realism—particularly valuable in a market as complex as wine.

3.4. Attributes and levels

The specification of attributes and their levels is essential for the validity of a DCE. Given the wide range of wine attributes, choice design requires careful consideration to prevent excessive complexity in choice tasks, which could increase error variance or lead to attribute non-attendance—a situation where certain attributes are ignored in the decision-making process (Heidenreich et al., 2018; Lizin et al., 2022; T. C. Nguyen et al., 2015). By using the dynamic reference-dependent choice approach, we implicitly account for all relevant wine attributes important for consumers’ preferences by holding them fixed while focusing on the specific attributes of interest in this study: pesticide reduction certification and price (summarized in Table 1). The level selection followed a similar approach to that used by Larvoe and Kallas (2025) to estimate the premium that organic wine consumers attributed to pesticide-free practices in their purchase decisions.

The pesticide reduction attribute is defined in terms of the percentage of chemical pesticide spray volume reduced through precision pest control technologies. The ongoing EU-funded Horizon 2020 NOVA-TERRA project in the Mediterranean region has established that vineyards can achieve up to 40 % pesticide reduction, depending on their commitment to innovative precision technologies (Escolà et al., 2013; Gil et al., 2023; Salas et al., 2024). Since the level of pesticide reduction depends on the winegrower’s scale and commitment to applying these technologies, a four-level pesticide reduction attribute is included to reflect different scales of commitment.

To accurately capture the premium for pesticide reduction, consumers must have this information, which could be guaranteed through certification or labels that are trusted, assuring them that the reductions are credible (Bazoche et al., 2014). As discussed in Section 2.2, certification entities for sustainable wines may be third-party EU-approved or private entities or first-/second-party-inspired entities such as participatory guarantee systems. Therefore, a four-level certification attribute is used, reflecting existing EU certification standards for sustainable food products (Bazoche et al., 2014; Cuéllar-Padilla and Ganuza-Fernandez, 2018). The first level is “no certification” (NC), which is common for most conventional wines. The second level involves certification by a private third-party entity (PC) mandated with regulatory powers to ensure compliance with production standards. The third level is participatory guarantee system certification (GC), a first- or second-party system based on the active participation of all stakeholders. The final level is certification by an EU-approved third-party entity (EC), which ensures compliance through entities mandated by the EU.

Finally, a four-level price attribute is included to correspond with the level of pesticide reduction. Considering the wide range of wine prices, designing choice experiments solely on the mean market price could result in unrealistic choice sets for some respondents due to under- or overpricing relative to their reference prices. Therefore, each respondent’s reference price (i.e., the price of the recently purchased conventional red wine) was used to generate the four price levels. This

Table 1
Attributes definitions and levels used in the choice experiment.

Attribute	Definition	Base	Level1	Level2	Level3
Pesticide reduction (continuous)	The percentage of spray volume of chemical pesticides reduced by conventional winegrowers using pesticide-reducing innovations	−10 %	−20 %	−30 %	−40 %
Certification (categorical)	Regulatory entities capable of issuing certificates to signal compliance with accepted sustainable practices	No certification (NC)	Private third-party certification (PC)	Participatory guarantee certification (GC)	EU-approved third-party certification (EC)
Price (continuous)	Price variation in percentage based on respondents’ stated reference prices in Euros (€) for a 750 ml bottle of red wine for regular home consumption	+5 %	+20 %	+35 %	+50 %

approach not only addresses the under- or overpricing effect but also allows our model to be estimated accurately, even if the sample is not representative of the entire wine population of the country (Feit et al., 2010).

3.5. Solemn oath and cheap talk script

A major criticism of stated preference methods is that the choices are made in hypothetical markets (Fifer et al., 2014) and are prone to hypothetical biases, i.e., respondents report unrealistic values because they are not obliged to commit to their stated values. Consumers are therefore likely to overlook the real cost since they do not actually pay, leading to the overstating of their WTP (Ajzen et al., 2004).

To minimize this bias, the solemn oath and cheap talk scripts below were used at the beginning of the questionnaire (Carlsson et al., 2005; De-Magistris and Pascucci, 2014). Thus, cheap talk and solemn oath scripts play the role of creating attitudes and intentions in a hypothetical situation that mimics those in a real situation (Ajzen et al., 2004).

Fig. 1 presents a summary of the two-step dynamic reference-dependent choice experiment, including a sample choice card. The design featured unlabeled alternatives and was developed using a D-efficient main effects design with constraints to ensure that higher pesticide reductions were paired with higher prices, and vice versa. The design was implemented using NGene™ software (Metrics, 2014) and yielded 16 choice sets, each containing three alternatives, which were randomly assigned to two blocks. Each respondent completed one block of eight choice sets.

3.6. Model estimation and hypothesis testing

The estimation of consumers’ WTP for wine produced with reduced pesticide use and the impact of certification on WTP is achieved using the random parameter logit (RPL) model (Greene, 2001). The RPL allows us to account for preference heterogeneity among decision-makers (consumers) in terms of their demographic, attitudinal and behavioral factors. Following the random utility theory of McFadden (1974), an individual *i*’s utility *U* obtained from the preferred alternative *j* consists of a deterministic observable part V_{ij} and a stochastic part ϵ_{ij} that accounts for unobservable factors. For each alternative *j* selected by the individual, the utility (U_{ij}) derived is the sum of the deterministic component (V_{ij}) and a random component (ϵ_{ij}):

$$U_{ij} = V_{ij} + \epsilon_{ij} \tag{1}$$

The deterministic component V_{ij} is specified as a linear additive expression of the function of the observed attributes of alternative *j* (X_{ij}), including the price and personal characteristics of the respondent. In this study, the attributes are reduced pesticide use (χ_{1ij}), certification type (χ_{2ij}), and price (χ_{3ij}). The individual-specific utility coefficients (β_i) are assumed to vary across respondents:

$$V_{ij} = \beta_{1i}\chi_{1ij} + \beta_{2i}\chi_{2ij} + \beta_{3i}\chi_{3ij} \tag{2}$$

To capture unobserved taste heterogeneity, the parameters β_{1i} , β_{2i} ,

<u>Cheap talk</u>	<u>Solemn oath</u>
<p><i>Caution! Studies show that people tend to act differently when they face hypothetical decisions. In other words, there are differences between what people say they will do and what they actually do in real markets. However, for this experiment, we want you to act in the same way that you would do if you had to actually pay for the wine and take it home. Please take into account how much you truly want the wine you choose relative to the others in each scenario.</i></p>	<p><i>I, the undersigned participant of this survey, do swear that during this experiment, I will tell the truth and always provide honest answers. Do you agree to this oath?</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">No <input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/></p>

and β_{3i} are specified as random draws from continuous probability distributions:

$$\beta_i \sim f(\beta|\theta) \tag{3}$$

where θ denotes the mean and standard deviation parameters of the distribution assumed for each random coefficient. The probability that individual i chooses alternative j is the integral of the standard logit probability over the distribution of β_i :

$$P_{ij} = \int \frac{\exp(\beta' \chi_{ij})}{\sum_{k \in J} \exp(\beta' \chi_{ik})} f(\beta|\theta) d\beta \tag{4}$$

where,

χ_{ij} is a vector of observed attributes for alternative j , individual i (i.e., reduced pesticide, certification type, and price), β is a vector of individual-specific coefficients, and $f(\beta|\theta)$ denotes the distribution of the random coefficients β , where θ represents the vector of distributional parameters, typically the means and standard deviations of each coefficient.

Since the integral lacks a closed-form solution, we approximate it using simulated maximum likelihood methods that are based on Halton sequences. The model parameters are then estimated by maximizing the simulated log-likelihood function. The estimated β coefficients capture the influence of wine attributes on choice probabilities and can be interpreted as utility weights, enabling formal tests of hypotheses H1 and H2.

3.6.1. Inclusion of personal characteristics

To test for preference heterogeneity (H3–H8) among consumers, we interact individual-level characteristics Z_i (demographics, attitudes, subjective knowledge, etc.) with the alternative-specific constant (ASC). The ASC is defined as one (1) if the individual selects any of the hypothetical red wine alternatives with reduced pesticide use and zero (0) if the "none" option is chosen, indicating a preference for the last conventionally purchased wine (Hanley et al., 2001; Schreiner and Latacz-Lohmann, 2024). The ASC therefore captures the average effect of all unobserved factors associated with alternative wines with reduced pesticide use.

$$V_{ij} = ASC_j + \beta' \chi_{ij} + \gamma'(Z_i + ASC_j) \tag{5}$$

where γ is the vector of interaction coefficients that estimate how personal characteristics affect the likelihood of choosing wines with reduced pesticide use.

3.6.2. Estimation of WTP

The consumers' WTP for each non-price attribute is calculated as the negative ratio of the partial derivative of the utility function with respect to that attribute (e.g., reduced pesticide use) to the partial derivative with respect to the price attribute (Van Loo et al., 2011). Accordingly, the WTP for an attribute such as reduced pesticide use is given by the negative ratio of its estimated coefficient β_1 to the estimated coefficient

of the price variable β_{price}

$$WTP_{x_1} = - \frac{\delta U_{ij} / \delta x_1}{\delta U_{ij} / \delta x_3} = - \frac{\beta_1}{\beta_3} \tag{6}$$

WTP estimates were computed using the sample means, and 95 % confidence intervals were derived to account for statistical uncertainty. In this study, we assume that the coefficients for all non-price attributes follow normal distributions, allowing for both positive and negative preference heterogeneity across individuals (Bliemer and Rose, 2013). Model estimation was performed using NLOGIT 6, a software package tailored for advanced econometric and discrete choice modeling (Greene, 2018).

3.7. Definition of variables

We present in Table 2 a summary of the variables used to test hypotheses H3 to H8, along with their means and coding. We examined the impact of sociodemographic factors on consumers' WTP under hypothesis H3 through the following variables: gender (H3a), coded as 1 for male and 0 for female; age (H3b), categorized into five groups ranging from 1 (18–24) to 5 (55+); and education (H3c), ranging from 1 (primary education) to 5 (master's degree or higher). For hypothesis H4, where we investigate the impact of environmental knowledge and awareness on WTP, two variables were used: subjective knowledge of pesticide use (H4a), measured on an ordinal scale from 1 (no knowledge) to 7 (expert knowledge) in response to the following question: "What is your level of knowledge regarding the use of pesticides in vineyards?", and exposure to pesticide-reducing innovations (H4b), coded as 1 for respondents who saw a sample innovation and 0 otherwise.

Under hypothesis H5, environmental attitude was measured by consumers' concerns about the negative impacts of pesticides on a scale from 1 (not concerned) to 7 (extremely concerned). The economic situation of consumers (H6) is analyzed through income level (H6a), categorized from 1 (<€1000) to 7 (>€6000), and the previous purchase price (H6b), measured in euros per 750 ml bottle. Under hypothesis H7, we assess the effect of consumer involvement on their WTP, using their wine involvement (H7a), measured with a wine involvement scale,³ a multi-dimensional scale measuring participation in wine-related activities (e.g., tasting, collecting), and purchase involvement (H7b), the number of times participants purchase wine in a year. Finally, under hypothesis H8, we measured respondents' exploratory behavior using the adapted wine neophobia scale, which measures openness to trying new wine products based on responses to specific statements (Rabadán, 2021b). The sample of the questionnaire in the Appendix provides further details on how each variable was measured.

To ensure the robustness of our results, we conducted key diagnostic checks. Multicollinearity among sociodemographic, attitudinal, and

³ Wine involvement measured with a multi-dimensional construct developed from (Bruwer and Huang, 2012; Rabadán, 2021b).

Stage one

1. Price of reference wine: Please indicate how much you usually pay for the standard **750 ml red wine** for your regular consumption at home (if in doubt, please state the price of your last purchase).
Response ---XX---€

2. Attributes of reference wine: Please indicate the importance of each of the following wine features to you when choosing your **red wine** for regular home consumption (*Note: Fourteen wine attributes were listed, and consumers rated their importance on an 11-point Likert scale*).

Stage two

3. Background of choice experiment: Winegrowers are increasingly adopting practices to reduce the environmental impact of viticulture. This includes the use of alternative farming innovations by conventional producers to lower the volume of chemical pesticides applied in vineyards. These wines may be certified by a recognized certification body or remain uncertified, and they may be priced slightly higher than the conventional wines you usually purchase.

4. Choice question framing: In your previous response, you indicated that you typically pay **XX €** for a **750 ml bottle of red wine** for regular home consumption and that you considered the following attributes during your purchase: (*attributes ranked above average inserted here*). Now, consider the following 750 ml red wine options. Which one would you choose for your regular home consumption? Please **imagine** that all options are from the **same brand** and have the **same characteristics** as the wine you last purchased—except for differences in the level of **pesticide use, certification, and price**.

Wine 1

30% Pesticide reduction

Third-party private certification

(XX + 15%) €

Wine 2

20% Pesticide reduction

No certification

(XX + 5%) €

None
(I prefer my last purchase)

Fig. 1. Summarized steps in dynamic reference-dependent choice experiment with an example of the choice sets presented to respondents. [For example, if a consumer indicated the price of the reference wine was 5€, the prices displayed for Wine1 and Wine2 are 5.75€ and 5.25€, respectively].

choice attributes was assessed using variance inflation factors (VIFs), all of which were less than 2.5 (mean \approx 1.5), indicating no serious multicollinearity issues (O'Brien, 2007). Additionally, to maintain the integrity of the reference prices in the dynamic DCE, we conducted a boxplot analysis to identify outliers and trim extreme purchase prices ($<€1.5$ or $>€25$), aligning the data with realistic market prices for standard conventional wines in all five countries.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive statistics

The survey data summarized in Table A1 in the appendix are based on responses from the five countries included in the study. The respondents are composed of mainly buyers of conventional wines (averaging 79%), who purchase wine regularly and are involved mainly in the purchase decision. The cleaned dataset, made of only conventional buyers, includes nearly 1000 respondents per country, with a range of backgrounds in wine-related activities, sociodemographics, knowledge of, and concerns about pesticide use in vineyards. The

Table 2
Summary of the variables used to test the hypotheses of the factors influencing WTP (N = 3960).

Main factor and sub-variables		Variable coding	Mean				
			FR	GR	IT	PT	ES
Sociodemographic (H3)							
H3a	Gender	1 = male, 0 = female	0.49	0.47	0.51	0.49	0.49
H3b	Age	1–5 (0 = 18–24, 5 = 55+ years)	3.62	3.66	3.67	3.55	3.56
H3c	Education	1–5 (1 = primary, 5 = master's or above)	3.52	3.43	3.35	3.52	3.43
Environmental knowledge (H4)							
H4a	Subjective knowledge of pesticide use in vines	1–7 (1 = no knowledge, 7 = expert)	2.17	2.57	2.45	2.18	2.23
H4b	Exposure to pesticide-reducing innovation	1 = see description, otherwise 0	0.50	0.48	0.50	0.52	0.49
Environmental attitude (H5)							
H5	Concern about pesticides' impact on environment	1–7 (1 = no concern, 7 = extremely concerned)	4.32	4.83	4.77	4.82	4.42
Economic situation (H6)							
H6a	Income level	1–7 (1 = <1000€, 7 = >6000€)	3.00	1.90	2.40	1.84	2.39
H6b	Previous purchase price	Euros € per 750 ml bottle	7.12	5.84	6.83	4.88	6.86
Consumer involvement (H7)							
H7a	Wine involvement	Continuous (wine involvement scale)	63.28	63.37	63.35	61.39	63.96
H7b	Purchase involvement	Continuous (frequency of wine purchase in a year)	5.58	4.56	5.40	5.39	6.44
Exploratory behavior (H8)							
H8	Openness to trying a new wine	Continuous (adapted wine neophobia scale)	32.21	31.95	34.33	33.65	32.95
TOTAL			716	765	717	934	828

FR = France, GR = Greece, IT = Italy, PT = Portugal and ES = Spain.

sample is well balanced in terms of gender, with nearly equal male and female representation, and spans age groups from young adults (18–24 years) to those over 55 years, providing a representative snapshot of consumer sentiment across different age and gender segments. Educational backgrounds vary widely, from secondary education to post-graduate levels, allowing for insights from consumers with diverse levels of formal education. Additionally, a broad distribution of income levels (from less than 1000 € to over 5000 € per month) captures the economic diversity of wine consumers across the countries studied.

With respect to awareness and concerns about pesticide use in vineyards and its environmental impact, the data reveal variability among consumers. The respondents reported a range of familiarity with pesticides, from little to extensive awareness, and expressed concerns that spanned from “no concern” to “very high concern.” Overall, the sociodemographic profile of the respondents aligns with the typical wine consumer profile observed in similar studies (Parga-Dans et al., 2023), making the dataset well suited for capturing consumer preferences for sustainable conventional wine, specifically those with reduced pesticide use.

4.2. Characteristics of the reference wines

The attributes of the respondents' most recently purchased conventional wines, detailed in Table A2 in the Appendix, reveal notable differences across the five countries in price, purchasing habits, and valued attributes. The average price paid for the last wine purchase varied significantly: €7.12 in France, €5.84 in Greece, €6.83 in Italy, €4.88 in Portugal, and €6.86 in Spain. Supermarkets and wine shops were the most common purchasing locations, although Italians also showed a greater tendency to buy wine online. Most respondents reported medium to high satisfaction with their most recent wine purchases, with the mean value indicating that consumers across the five countries were either satisfied or highly satisfied.

The most important attributes of consumers during purchase also differ by country. French buyers prioritized taste, price, and brand, while Greeks emphasized origin, taste, and price, and Italians valued taste, price, and origin. Portuguese consumers focused on price, taste, and brand, whereas Spanish buyers highlighted price, brand, and taste. These variations reflect the influence of local markets and cultural differences on consumer behavior.

Given the diverse backgrounds of the consumers, a pooled model was deemed unsuitable, as it risked oversimplifying the data and producing

biased estimates. Instead, country-specific models were used to provide a more accurate and unbiased understanding of consumer WTP in each country.

4.3. Results of the random parameter logit model

The results of the RPL model are reported in Table 3, where all the coefficients are estimated with the sample means, along with their standard errors. Additionally, the WTP values and their 95 % confidence intervals for the pesticide reduction attribute and three certification types are calculated from the RPL with “no certification” as the base category. The RPL model shows good statistical fit across all countries, with McFadden's pseudo R² values ranging between 0.28 and 0.32.

To assess the appropriateness and robustness of the RPL model, we compared the RPL results to corresponding standard multinomial logit models. The RPL specifications yielded substantially higher log-likelihood values and lower AIC and BIC values relative to the MNL models, indicating superior model performance (see Table A4 in the Appendix). A likelihood ratio test additionally confirmed that the RPL models significantly outperformed the MNL models (p < 0.001), suggesting the presence of unobserved preference heterogeneity and justifying the use of the RPL framework.

Additionally, the contribution of the independent variables to the model fit was examined by comparing three RPL model specifications: a base model with only ASCs, a model including product choice attributes, and a full model including both choice attributes and interaction terms (see Table A5 in the Appendix). Across all countries, the inclusion of choice attributes significantly improved model fit relative to the ASC-only model, and the addition of interaction terms further enhanced model performance. Likelihood ratio tests confirmed that these improvements were highly significant (p < 0.001), indicating the robustness and explanatory power of the full RPL specification.

4.4. WTP for wine with reduced pesticide use and certification (H1 and H2)

The estimated coefficient for the price attribute shows the expected negative sign, indicating that as the price increases, the likelihood of choosing wine with reduced pesticide use decreases. This aligns with the general demand theory that prices have a negative effect on preferences. The coefficients for ASC are significant and largely positive across all countries, suggesting a strong preference for conventional wines with

Table 3
Results of the random parameter logit (RPL) model with WTP estimates.

Attributes	France	Greece	Italy	Portugal	Spain
Pesticide reduction	0.023***	0.024***	0.017***	0.025***	0.024***
Standard errors	(0.006)	(0.005)	(0.006)	(0.005)	(0.006)
WTP (%/750 ml)	0.65	0.72	0.74	0.76	0.71
Confidence interval	[0.31, 0.78]	[0.63, 1.06]	[0.57, 1.16]	[0.40, 0.92]	[0.48, 0.88]
PC	0.176***			0.143***	-0.064*
Standard errors	(0.038)			(0.035)	(0.035)
WTP (%/750 ml)	4.51	-	-	4.33	-1.88
Confidence interval	[2.36, 6.13]			[2.13, 6.24]	[-3.89,-0.28]
GC	0.093**	0.177***	0.127***	0.043***	0.079**
Standard errors	(0.044)	(0.044)	(0.045)	(0.04)	(0.041)
WTP (%/750 ml)	2.43	5.36	5.52	1.30	2.32
Confidence interval	[1.58, 2.94]	[5.94, 8.21]	[4.81, 5.98]	[0.93, 1.93]	[1.92, 2.86]
EC	0.285***	0.292***	0.159***	0.213***	0.200***
Standard errors	(0.043)	(0.062)	(0.054)	(0.052)	(0.051)
WTP (%/750 ml)	7.31	8.84	6.90	6.45	5.88
Confidence interval	[6.82, 7.88]	[7.10, 9.30]	[1.20, 3.90]	[4.51, 7.90]	[4.20, 6.80]
Price	-0.039***	-0.033***	-0.023***	-0.033***	-0.034***
Standard errors	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.002)
ASC	1.352***	1.330***	1.086***	1.433***	1.234***
Standard errors	(0.075)	(0.076)	(0.078)	(0.072)	(0.072)
No of obs. (N)	17,184	18,360	17,208	22,416	19,872
McFadden R ²	0.279	0.302	0.303	0.323	0.314
Log-likelihood (LL)	-677.800	-995.486	-913.121	-928.808	-677.801
Akaike Inf. Criteria (AIC)	1423.6	2459.0	1894.2	1925.6	1877.1

Levels of significance: ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1.

Model estimated considering 500 Halton sequences. PC: private third-party certification; GC: participatory guarantee certification; EC: EU-approved certification; ASC: alternative specific constant. WTP: willingness to pay; Blank (-): not statistically significant.

reduced pesticide use over standard conventional reference wines.

The estimated WTP for wine produced with reduced pesticide use shows that consumers in France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain are willing to pay 0.65 %, 0.72 %, 0.74 %, 0.76 %, and 0.71 % more, respectively, for a standard 750 ml red wine produced with a 1 % reduction in the volume of pesticide use compared with standard conventional practices. This finding indicates that consumers are willing to pay a premium for wines with lower pesticide use, with the highest premium in Portugal (0.76 %) and the lowest in France (0.65 %).

Regarding certification, the results consistently show that EU-approved third-party certification is the most highly valued certification across all five countries. Compared with wine without certification, consumers are willing to pay a higher premium for this certification, with WTP values of 7.31 % in France, 8.84 % in Greece, 6.90 % in Italy, 6.45 % in Portugal, and 5.88 % in Spain. The premiums on wines with private third-party certification and participatory guarantee certification vary across countries. For example, in France and Portugal, consumers are willing to pay a higher premium for wines with private third-party certification than for those with participatory guarantee certification. Conversely, in Greece, Italy, and Spain, participatory guarantee certification commands higher WTP over private third-party certification. However, in Greece and Italy, the WTP values for PCs are not statistically significant, indicating that there is no clear consumer preference for private certification in these countries.

Overall, the results show that EU-approved third-party certification is the most valued form of certification. Participatory guarantee certification ranks second, except in France and Portugal, where private third-party certifications are preferred over participatory guarantee types.

The results strongly confirm the two hypotheses that consumers place a significant premium on pesticide reduction as a sustainable wine attribute (H1) and that EU-approved certifications lead to greater WTP than other certifications do (H2).

4.5. Factors influencing WTP for wine with reduced pesticide use (H3–H8)

The results of the six hypotheses, tested via 11 measurable variables interacting with the ASC in the RPL model, are presented in Table 4. To evaluate the influence of these variables on WTP for wine produced with reduced pesticides, as proposed in the hypotheses, the coefficients of the interaction terms were divided by the price coefficient, as expressed in Equation (4). Only significant WTP values are reported, with positive values indicating that the variable increases WTP but negative values suggesting otherwise, ceteris paribus.

H3. Sociodemographics

H3a. (Gender): The role of gender was significant only in Greece, with an estimated WTP premium of 14.94 % for wines with reduced pesticide use. This suggests that men are willing to pay more for conventional wines with reduced pesticides than women are willing to do, contrary to our hypothesis.

H3b. (Age): In France (-21.77 %), Portugal (-19.58 %), and Spain (-17.68 %), older consumers put a lower premium on wines with reduced pesticides, confirming our hypothesis that younger consumers are willing to pay more for sustainable products.

In contrast, in Greece (16.09 %), older consumers are willing to pay more, indicating a stronger preference for pesticide reduction among older consumers, contrary to our hypotheses.

H3c. (Education): The education hypothesis was confirmed only in Portugal (27.12 %), suggesting that highly educated consumers demonstrated greater WTP.

H4. Knowledge and awareness

H4a. (Subjective knowledge about pesticide use): In Portugal (6.42 %) and Spain (11.82 %), consumers who perceive themselves as knowledgeable about pesticide use in winegrowing are willing to pay higher premiums, confirming our hypothesis that awareness drives demand for

Table 4
Factors influencing consumer WTP for wines with reduced pesticide use.

	France	Greece	Italy	Portugal	Spain
Sociodemographics (H3)					
H3a x ASC	–	14.94***	–	28.42***	–
Confidence interval		[11.24, 19.25]		[22.15, 35.25]	
H3b x ASC	–21.77***	–	16.09**	–19.58**	–17.68**
Confidence interval	[31.21, 16.24]		[11.32, 21.80]	[–25.62, 14.82]	[–23.65, 12.69]
H3c x ASC	–	–	–	27.12***	–
Confidence interval				[24.32, 32.45]	
Perceived knowledge (H4)					
H4a x ASC	–	–	–	6.42***	11.82***
Confidence interval				[3.16, 9.16]	[8.54, 15.32]
H4b x ASC	24.85***	–	31.13*	23.70***	25.50***
Confidence interval	[18.25, 29.35]		[26.56, 37.58]	[18.56, 29.64]	[19.64, 29.57]
Environmental attitude (H5)					
H5 x ASC	–	10.06**	–	14.79***	16.35**
Confidence interval		[7.25, 14.25]		[10.56, 18.35]	[12.86, 21.45]
Economic factors (H6)					
H6a x ASC	21.64***	–	–	34.42**	12.82**
Confidence interval	[19.25, 25.65]			[31.91, 38.24]	[8.21, 15.25]
H6b x ASC	3.05***	–	14.70**	4.00	5.81**
Confidence interval	[1.05, 5.16]		[9.18, 18.96]	[2.11, 67.24]	[2.25, 6.18]
Consumer involvements (H7)					
H7a x ASC	1.10*	1.30**	–	–	–
Confidence interval	[0.38, 2.97]	[0.24, 2.88]			
H7b x ASC	–	–	28.87*	24.48***	–
Confidence interval			[22.36, 34.27]	[19.25, 27.35]	
Exploratory behavior (H8)					
H8 x ASC	–2.10*	–	–4.09***	–	–
Confidence interval	[–5.31, 0.85]		[–6.58, 1.89]		

Levels of significance: ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1.

Note: Estimates are obtained by dividing the coefficients of the interaction terms by the coefficient of price of the respective countries. All values are percentages because the price attribute is a percentage.

Blank (–): not statistically significant; ASC: alternative specific constant; H3a: gender; H3b: age; H3c: education; H4a: subjective knowledge of pesticide use in vineyards; H4b: exposure to pesticide-reducing innovations; H5: concern about the impact of pesticide use on the environment; H6a: income level; H6b: previous purchase price; H7a: wine involvement; H7b: purchase involvement; H8: openness to new wine.

sustainable products.

H4b. (Exposure to pesticide-reducing innovations): Consumers in France (24.85 %), Italy (31.13 %), Portugal (23.70 %), and Spain (25.50 %), who were exposed to samples of technologies developed to limit pesticide use in vineyards, are willing to pay significantly higher premiums, supporting the hypothesis that exposure to innovative practices increases subjective knowledge, which in turn positively impacts consumer WTP.

H5. Environmental attitudes

Concern about the environmental impacts of pesticide use: Consumers with greater environmental concerns are willing to pay a premium of 10.06 % in Greece, 14.79 % in Portugal, and 16.35 % in Spain. These results point to a link between positive environmental attitudes and the willingness to support sustainable wine production, as we hypothesized.

H6. Economic factors

H6a. (Income level): Higher-income consumers are willing to pay more—21.64 % in France, 34.42 % in Portugal, and 12.82 % in Spain. This finding supports our hypothesis and suggests that financial capacity positively influences the demand for sustainable wine.

H6b. (Previous purchase price): Consumers with higher stated prices for their last purchased wines are also willing to pay more for reduced-pesticide wines: 3.05 % in France, 14.70 % in Italy, and 5.81 % in Spain. This confirms our hypothesis that premium wine buyers value sustainable pesticide reduction more.

H7. Consumer involvement

H7a. (Wine involvement): In France (1.10 %) and Greece (1.30 %), consumers with greater involvement in wine-related activities are willing to pay slightly higher premiums for wines with reduced pesticide use, partially supporting our hypothesis.

H7b. (Purchase involvement): In Greece (28.87 %) and Portugal (24.48 %), consumers who purchase wines more frequently are willing to pay significantly higher premiums. This suggests that frequent and actively involved consumers place a higher value on sustainability attributes, which confirms our hypothesis.

H8. Exploratory behavior

Openness to new wine: In France (–2.10 %) and Portugal (–4.09 %), consumers who are more open to trying new wines are unwilling to pay more for conventional wines with reduced pesticide use, rejecting our hypothesis that open-minded consumers could view pesticide reduction to be a more valuable attribute.

Overall, the factors influencing WTP varied across the five countries, with the data confirming the expected relationships in some countries whereas others were rejected or showed no statistical significance. Consistent patterns were observed for variables such as age, education, environmental attitudes, and economic factors, while differences in gender and exploratory behavior highlighted country-specific deviations.

5. Discussion

With the recent withdrawal of the EU Sustainable Use of Pesticide Regulation following sustained political and farmer resistance, the challenge of reducing pesticide use in agriculture remains unresolved. In this context, our study offers timely and policy-relevant insights into how consumer preferences may complement regulatory approaches in advancing sustainability within viticulture. The results from five key Mediterranean wine-producing countries show that consumers are willing to pay a measurable premium for conventional wines produced with reduced pesticide use, independent of organic certification. This confirms that specific environmentally beneficial practices, when credibly signaled, are valued in the market and can incentivize more sustainable production. Notably, EU-approved third-party certifications attract the highest consumer trust and willingness to pay, underscoring the importance of credible labeling in shaping purchasing decisions. By isolating the impact of pesticide reduction from broader certification effects and identifying key socioeconomic and attitudinal drivers of demand, this study provides a robust foundation for repositioning sustainable conventional wines and guiding future marketing and policy efforts in a post-SUR policy landscape.

5.1. Opportunities for conventional winegrowers

The findings reveal a significant opportunity for conventional wine producers in the EU Mediterranean region to leverage pesticide-reduction technologies as a value-added strategy. Based on the estimated WTP, a 1 % reduction in pesticide use corresponds to consumer

premiums that scale meaningfully with greater reductions. For example, adopting technologies such as those demonstrated in the EU NOVA-TERRA project, which have achieved up to 40 % pesticide reductions, could translate into price premiums of approximately 26 % in France, 29 % in Greece, 30 % in Italy and Portugal, and 28 % in Spain, assuming that all other factors remain constant. However, realizing this potential depends critically on transparent and credible communication of these sustainability efforts to consumers. The study underscores the pivotal role of EU-approved third-party certifications in this regard, as they command the highest level of consumer trust and serve as effective mechanisms for signaling environmental performance (Delmas and Gergaud, 2021; Delmas and Grant, 2014). By bridging the information gap between producers and consumers, these certifications can help translate sustainable practices, such as pesticide reduction, into tangible market rewards (Morone et al., 2021; Sogari et al., 2016).

5.2. Positioning sustainable conventional wines

While prior research has focused primarily on consumer WTP for organic, biodynamic, or natural wines (Barisan et al., 2024; Schäufele and Hamm, 2017; Tait et al., 2019; Vecchio et al., 2023), these practices often pose technical, financial, and operational challenges for many winegrowers (Merot et al., 2019; Merot and Smits, 2024). This study highlights the potential of sustainable conventional practices, such as pesticide reduction, to attract significant consumer premiums, offering an alternative pathway for sustainability. For example, a comparison of WTP for wines with a 40 % reduction in pesticides across the five countries (26–30 %) with previous works on organic wine premiums suggests that conventional wines from pesticide-reduced practices command a premium closer to the value consumers attribute to organic options. Scozzafava et al. (2021), for instance, reported a 36 % price premium for organic wines relative to standard conventional wines. The significant premium for pesticide-reduced wines suggests an untapped “middle ground” for wines that bridge the gap between standard conventional and organic categories. These wines could expand the sustainable wine market, appealing to environmentally conscious consumers while providing a feasible option for winegrowers hesitant to fully transition to organic methods (D’Amico et al., 2016; Siepmann and Nicholas, 2018).

5.3. Consistency across sustainability attributes

The average WTP estimate for wines with 40 % reduced pesticide use—approximately 28.6 % across five countries—aligns closely with Li and Kallas’ (2021) reported average premium of 29.5 % for sustainability attributes. This convergence underscores the consistent value consumers place on environmental improvements across diverse contexts. Reducing pesticide use could thus serve as a compelling entry point for producers seeking to tap into the growing market for sustainable products. By achieving premiums comparable to broader sustainability certifications, producers can appeal to a mainstream audience increasingly driven by eco-conscious purchasing decisions (Gilinsky et al., 2016; Santini et al., 2013; Schäufele and Hamm, 2017).

5.4. The role of certification

The results show that certification remains a cornerstone of consumer trust in sustainable wine claims, as highlighted in previous research (Morone et al., 2021; Sogari et al., 2016). This trust is particularly relevant given that premium prices for sustainability labels are highly heterogeneous and depend significantly on the type and quality of information disclosed (Piracci et al., 2024). While some previous studies suggest that self-declaration may yield higher prices for winegrowers (Fanusch and Frick, 2020), this research shows that credible certification entities significantly influence consumer premiums for pesticide reduction. Without such certification, claims of limited

pesticide use lack verification, diminishing consumer confidence and WTP.

EU-approved certifications, which are perceived as rigorous and accountable, have emerged as the most trusted among consumers, reinforcing the critical role of trusted bodies in communicating sustainability claims. Policymakers could leverage this trust by integrating pesticide reduction information into existing certification schemes, making such claims more transparent and credible. Additionally, enhancing labeling regulations to include detailed pesticide-use footprints could empower winegrowers to communicate their practices more effectively. This approach aligns with consumer preferences for verified sustainability claims and could drive broader adoption of eco-friendly practices in the wine industry (Brach et al., 2018).

5.5. Understanding consumer heterogeneity and drivers

The results reveal nuanced drivers of consumer WTP for sustainable wines, particularly those produced with reduced pesticide use. Across six hypotheses, including sociodemographics, environmental attitudes, consumer involvement, economic factors, exploratory behavior, and knowledge, both consistent patterns and country-specific deviations emerge. Income, age, gender, environmental awareness, and wine-related involvement significantly shape WTP across contexts, which aligns with prior findings (Barber et al., 2009; Katt and Meixner, 2020; Mauracher et al., 2019; Nandi et al., 2017). In France and Portugal, novelty-seeking consumers did not perceive pesticide reduction as a strong value added, suggesting that product experimentation may be driven more by taste, region, or branding than by sustainability attributes. In contrast, older consumers in Greece exhibited a higher WTP, possibly due to stronger health concerns or deeper-rooted environmental values (Hamzaoui Essoussi and Linton, 2010; Ma and Xing, 2024; van Doorn and Verhoef, 2011).

These findings emphasize the importance of cultural and market-specific dynamics in shaping preferences, reinforcing the need for segmentation strategies that address diverse motivations within the wine market.

5.6. Implications for marketing and policy

The eleven factors identified as influencing consumer WTP for wines with reduced pesticide use provide valuable insights for both marketing strategies and policy design aimed at advancing sustainable viticulture. Demographically, younger consumers, particularly Millennials and Gen Z, have consistently shown higher willingness to pay across most countries, supporting earlier research that links sustainable consumption to younger cohorts (Ghaffar and Islam, 2024; Gomes et al., 2023). However, the notably high WTP among older consumers in Greece highlights the need for marketing strategies tailored to both generational and regional contexts. These findings suggest that messaging should avoid one-size-fits-all approaches in favor of segmentation strategies that reflect cultural and demographic diversity.

Subjective knowledge, exposure to innovative practices, and pro-environmental attitudes also emerged as strong predictors of WTP, underscoring the importance of consumer education. For example, exposure to examples of pesticide-reducing innovations significantly increased WTP in all countries except Greece, demonstrating the power of targeted information in shaping consumer behavior. Income and prior purchase experience further suggest that sustainability attributes resonate most strongly with higher-income and premium wine buyers, offering producers a clear opportunity to align environmental benefits with added market value.

These insights are particularly timely given the European Commission’s recent decision to suspend the SUR, initially proposed under the EU Green Deal. In place of binding reduction targets, the EU now intends to fast-track the approval of biopesticides and alternative crop protection technologies. While this shift emphasizes innovation, it also signals

the challenges of achieving regulatory consensus amid farmer resistance and political opposition.

In this policy vacuum, consumer-driven incentives such as WTP can serve as powerful levers for sustainability. Voluntary action by producers, motivated by market demand, may represent the most viable path toward reducing pesticide use. Our findings suggest that targeted marketing, combined with consumer education and transparent labeling, can effectively stimulate demand for wines produced using pesticide-reducing practices.

Policymakers and industry stakeholders should therefore consider complementing innovation-driven strategies with tools that harness consumer preferences. Certification schemes, eco-labels, and incentive programs that reward producers for meeting voluntary reduction targets could help build momentum toward more sustainable grape production. In an evolving policy landscape, such market-based signals may become increasingly central to achieving meaningful environmental outcomes.

5.7. Limitations and future research

While the study achieves its objectives and offers meaningful insights into consumer WTP for reduced pesticide use in wine production, a few limitations should be acknowledged to contextualize the findings and inform future research.

First, the data were obtained through a self-reported survey, which may be subject to social desirability bias and hypothetical bias, where respondents overstate their environmentally conscious preferences. Although steps were taken to mitigate these effects, including the use of a solemn oath script, cheap talk instructions, and a large representative sample, these biases cannot be entirely eliminated. Thus, while the findings are directionally robust, they should be interpreted with due caution, particularly when extrapolating to actual market behavior.

Second, although the dynamic reference-dependent DCE offers a more realistic and cognitively manageable way to capture consumer preferences, its design may inherently over-emphasize selected attributes, in this case, pesticide reduction and certification. This could inflate the estimated WTP values for the attributes under investigation, even though the design simultaneously reduces attribute non-attendance and choice complexity. Future research could expand on this approach by incorporating a broader range of wine attributes, such as origin designations (PDO/PGI), brand reputation, or sensory qualities, into the experimental design, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of how consumers weigh pesticide reduction alongside other key wine characteristics.

Furthermore, while the reference-dependent design improves external validity by anchoring choices to real-world purchasing behavior, variation in the diversity of reference wines across respondents may influence baseline comparisons. Future studies could improve accuracy by clustering participants with similar purchase histories to refine the reference price calibration.

In addition, the use of a Qualtrics research panel, while effective in accessing a large and demographically varied sample, may limit the generalizability of the findings. Specifically, the results may under-represent less digitally engaged populations or wine consumers who purchase through traditional, non-digital channels. Future research should explore hybrid data collection strategies, including in-person or retail-based recruitment, to reach broader segments of the wine-consuming public.

Finally, while this study focused on testing aggregate consumer preferences using sociodemographic and attitudinal factors, future research could apply latent class analysis or cluster-based segmentation to uncover deeper heterogeneity in preferences. Identifying distinct consumer segments would enrich the understanding of how different groups value pesticide reduction relative to other wine attributes. Moreover, similar investigations could be extended to other processed conventional foods and beverages, broadening insights into how market-based mechanisms can complement regulatory approaches in

advancing sustainable environmental practices in vineyards.

6. Conclusion

This study examined wine consumers' willingness to support pesticide reduction in EU Mediterranean vineyards by examining their willingness to pay for conventional wines produced with reduced pesticide use. Using a dynamic, reference-dependent discrete choice experiment across five major wine-producing countries—France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain, the findings reveal that consumers are willing to pay a significant premium for such wines compared with standard conventional options. The results also underscore the critical role of certification bodies in signaling sustainability. Consumers consistently value EU-recognized certification more than private or producer-led alternatives, highlighting the importance of institutional trust in shaping sustainable consumption. WTP is further influenced by a range of individual factors, including sociodemographic characteristics, environmental attitudes, the economic situation, sustainability knowledge, product involvement, and exploratory behavior. By focusing on a specific sustainable practice within conventional production systems rather than a full organic transition, this study extends the WTP literature and shows that partial sustainability efforts can attract market support. These insights offer actionable guidance for producers and policymakers aiming to align agricultural practices with consumer preferences and environmental goals.

Overall, the findings support the potential for consumer-driven market incentives to complement regulatory efforts toward pesticide reduction. They also contribute to broader sustainability objectives under the EU Green Deal and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly those promoting responsible consumption, environmental protection, and sustainable agriculture.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Noah Larvoe: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Yasmina Baba:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Felicidad De Herralde:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Zein Kallas:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.145979>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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